

pH Dependence of Solubility of Lead Hydroxylapatite and its Solid Solutions with Arsenate

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The solubility of Lead Hydroxylapatite and its solid solutions with arsenate in the physiologically important pH range of 5.0 to 8.0 decreases with increase in the pH of the medium of dissolution. This is due to the dissolved phosphate ions function as proton acceptors and being salts of weak acid form undergoes hydrolysis in aqueous media and at a given pH it is found to increase steadily with increase in the arsenate content of the sample.

L EAD hydroxylapatite (PbHA), $Pb_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2$, is very important among the apatite series of compounds¹. $PO_4^{3-} \rightarrow (AsO_4)^{3-}$ exchange in PbHA is of biological importance. This exchange process results in the formation of solid solutions of lead hydroxylapatite with arsenate due to their closeness of their ionic radii according to the following equation

While the pH dependence of the solubility of PbHA has been thoroughly investigated² similar studies on its solid solutions with arsenate are not available. The present work reports a study of (i) the pH dependence of solubility of solid solutions of PbHA with arsenate in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0 and (ii) the solubility effect with increase of arsenate content in the solid solutions at a fixed pH value.

Experimental

The details of preparation and identification of PbHA and its solid solutions with arsenate were reported earlier³. The formation of solid solutions was further confirmed by X-ray diffraction study. The diffraction patterns of the samples was conducted on a Siemens diffractometer using CuK_{α} Ni-filtered radiation; 35 KV, 18 MA; scanning 2θ speed $1^\circ/\text{min}$; registration speed of 1 cm./min. The $d(hkl)$ indexes are given by comparison with the indexed spectrum of the ASTM file (Card No. 3-0578). The solubility studies were based exclusively on the micro analytical determination of lead in the solution of the samples. Acetic-acid-sodium acetate and sodium diethyl barbituratehydrochloric acid were used as buffer combinations. The pH was measured with a line operated Beckman pH meter before and after equilibration to ascertain its constancy. 0.2 g of 200 mesh (B.S.S.) solute was added to 100 ml of the buffer solution prepared in carbondioxide free double distilled water

Fig. 1. pH dependence of solubility of lead hydroxylapatite and its solid solutions with arsenate.

taken in a air tight polyethylene container and was shaken mechanically at a regulated speed at the room temperature (30°). At the end of the desired period of equilibration the systems were separately filtered through a porosity G₄ crucible and the lead content in the filtrate was determined complexometrically⁴.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analyses of the samples were given in columns 2-4 of Table 1 and a graphical representation of the solubility behaviour was shown in Fig. 1. The experimental wt% errors of the determinations of Pb²⁺, PO₄³⁻ and AsO₄³⁻ when present together as in the solid solutions were respectively ±0.5, negligible and ±0.8 while the corresponding errors when Pb²⁺ was present either PO₄³⁻ or AsO₄³⁻ were less than ±0.5. Based on the fact

that a mole of each sample has a total 6 g atoms of PO₄³⁻ and/or AsO₄³⁻, the molecular formulae of the samples were calculated from the results of columns 3-4 and included in column 5 of Table 1.

The g atom ratio, $\frac{Pb}{P+As}$, in a mole of each sample

was calculated from the results of columns 2-4 and given in column 6 of the Table 1. The experimentally

obtained gram atomic ratio $\frac{Pb}{P+As}$ per mole of each

sample was 1.675 (theoretical value 1.67) confirms the purity, and the formation of homogeneous solid solutions⁵. The X-ray diffraction data of a representative set of the samples namely, sample nos. 1, 3, 5 and 7 of Table 1 are given in Fig. 2. The lattice parameter values of *a* and *c* are gradually

TABLE I. CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF LEAD HYDROXYLAPATITE AND ITS SOLID SOLUTIONS WITH ARSENATE

Sample No.	Wt%			Molecular formula	Molecular volumes ml/mole	g.atom ratio Pb/P+As	Lattice parameters (Å)	
	Pb	P	As				a	c
1	77.45	6.95	—	Pb ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	363.1	1.68	9.68	7.22
2	76.26	5.82	2.49	Pb ₁₀ (PO ₄) _{5.1} (AsO ₄) _{0.9} (OH) ₂	366.0	1.76	9.93	7.24
3	75.04	4.61	5.14	Pb ₁₀ (PO ₄) _{4.1} (AsO ₄) _{1.9} (OH) ₂	367.0	1.67	10.01	7.27
4	73.75	3.31	8.01	Pb ₁₀ (PO ₄) _{3.0} (AsO ₄) _{3.0} (OH) ₂	369.0	1.67	10.09	7.30
5	72.85	2.40	10.02	Pb ₁₀ (PO ₄) _{2.2} (AsO ₄) _{3.8} (OH) ₂	369.3	1.68	10.15	7.33
6	71.52	0.11	13.56	Pb ₁₀ (PO ₄) _{1.0} (AsO ₄) _{5.0} (OH) ₂	369.8	1.68	10.26	7.37
7	70.46	—	15.31	Pb ₁₀ (AsO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	371.2	1.68	10.33	7.40

Fig. 2. X-ray diffraction spectra of PbHA and its solid solutions with arsenate. (Spectra of sample nos. 1, 3, 5 and 7 of Table 1).

increasing with the increase in arsenate content in the samples. It is found true because whenever there is a substitution of a bigger ion like $(AsO_4)^{3-}$ in place of $(PO_4)^{3-}$ there will be a dialation in its unit cell volume consequent upon increase in a and c parameter values. The dissolution of PbHA can be considered to be initiated by the hydrolysis of PO_4^{3-} of the hydroxylapatite lattice which leads to the formation of $Pb_3(PO_4)_2$ and $Pb(OH)_2$ according to the following equations

Exactly analogous equations can be proposed for the $Pb_{10}(AsO_4)_6(OH)_2$. So $Pb_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2$ and $Pb_{10}(AsO_4)_6(OH)_2$ basically undergo the same mole of dissolution leading to the formation of lead phosphate and lead hydroxide in the former case and arsenate and lead hydroxide in the latter case. The solubility of the samples at a given pH was expected to increase (Fig. 1A) when more of phosphate in PbHA was replaced by arsenate which lowers the lattice energy of the hydroxylapatite resulting in appreciable destabilisation of the lattice⁶—a well known phenomena observed in allotropy when the

less stable allotropes are more soluble, e.g. aragonite (ortho-rhombic) is less stable and hence has greater solubility than calcite having a more symmetrical rhombohedral crystal lattice. The decrease of the solubility of the samples (Fig. 1B) in each case with increase in pH could be explained on the basis of the common-ion effect applied to the solubility products.

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